

Women and Higher Education in India

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Introduction

Higher education means the education beyond the level of secondary education. It is often assumed that education imparted by the college (or) universities are higher education. But in fact higher educational institutions include professional schools in the field of law, Theology, Medicine, Business, Music and Art. It also includes other institutions like Teacher Training school and Technological Institutions. Moreover, institutions for training of highly skilled specialists in the field of economics, science, technology and culture of various types of higher school are treated as higher educational Institutions. Because these institutions allow those candidates in their campus who have completed their study at the secondary level. Thus in general the term Higher Education refers the education at the degree level and above.

Background of Higher Education in India

In India Higher Education had its roots in early time as well. In the 5th century BC Taxila was the earliest recorded centre of higher education in India although there is a debate with its status-whether it was university (or) not. In the modern sense of the term university the Nalanda University was the oldest university system of education in the world. With the establishment of the British Raj in India, the western educations become ingrained into Indian society. But in the pre-independence era there was very limited access to higher education. From the year 1883 till the independence both the number of colleges and the enrollment of students in India were found to be very low. The following table will show the picture of higher education in India from pre independence to post independence

Picture of Higher Education in India from preindependence to post independence.

Table 1

Year	1883	1928	1947	1961-62
No. of colleges	139	307	591	2282
No of Enrolment	16088	90677	228881	1177245

Growth of Higher Education in India

India occupies an important position in respect of higher education. . Comparing with other countries in the world, India's position in the field of higher education system is third after the United States and china. After independence numbers of both the higher education institutions and number of student have been increasing. The following table will show the picture.

Institution of Higher Education and their Intake Capacity

Table 2

No. of university level institutions	25	117	320	367	467	544
No. of colleges	700	7346	16885	18064	25951	31324
Capacity indicators	1950	1991	2004	2006	2009	2010
No. of teachers (in thousands)	15	272	457	488	588	699
No. of students enrolled (in millions)	0.1	4.9	9.95	11.2	13.6	14.6

Thus since independence higher education in India has spread rapidly throughout India so much so that it is the third largest system in the world. This is because of the visionary planning of the leaders of our country.

Pice of Women in Higher Education in India

In India the female education has its roots in the British Regime. In 1854 the East India Company acknowledge women's education and employment. Intially this education was limited only to primary school level education and only the richer section of the society enjoyed this facility. Thus as it was confined only for a small section of people in society so the literacy rate for women increased from 0.2% in 1882 to 6% only in 1947. It is very unfortunate to say that for centuries higher education for women has been neglected.

In some elite institutions we find that number of female students is more than male students and there is a possibility to increase this trend. It is true that number of male is outnumbered in comparison with female. One of the reasons for this is rampant sex selection and cultural factors. It is common feature that from the time of birth girls are discriminated in subtle and crude ways. But in spite of this, it is a great advancement that the presence of women in colleges and universities are growing. Not only this, it is also found that in some most competitive higher educational institutions women are gaining entry without availing gender quote. This is undoubtedly credit for them.

The reason behind this neglecting attitude was biological differences. But today, in the 21st century none can ignore the necessity and urgency of higher education for women. Because now-a-days there is no biological differences. That is why all over the world higher education for women has gained a wider role and responsibility. In the third world countries the need for higher education among women is more important as because colonialism has remained a great force here which hinders education for the general masses and for women in particular.

Necessity of Higher Education for Women

Almost half of the population in India is occupied by women they are the half of the human resources. But it is very unfortunate to say that for long years there have been a strong bias against women and thereby there is a tendency to deny equal socio-economic opportunity for them. This neglecting attitude towards women is prominent in many respects particularly in the field of education. None can deny the fact that education is the fundamental agents for the socio-economic development of a country. But women access in the domain of education has not been fairly treated.

There are two different views on the question of women participation in higher education – traditional and modern. The traditional view supports women’s education to equip them to become better wives and mother. This view believes that women’s present education is entirely irrelevant in their lives. It is only waste of time and this does not help them to solve the problem of their daily life. This view believes that modern educated women are neither happy nor contented nor socially useful. She is misfit in life and needs opportunities for self expression. But modern attitude visualizes education as an instrument for women’s equality and development.

Women education has two aspect –individual aspect and social aspect. It is education which increases omens abilities to deal with the problem of her life, her family, her society and nation. Education increases confidence in a woman. Educated women can easily understand the demerits of early marriage and high birth rate. They have the attitude of gender parity among their children right from health care nutrition, education, and even career. The fruits of education are enjoyed not only by the women concerned but it passes to her family in later life. in a word, over all development of a society depends on the development of its total members. But if half of its members are legged behind, obviously it will create hindrance to the development.

Our past experience shows that higher education was restricted only to men. Women did not have any entry in the domain of higher education. Now a day this facility has been widened and women have equal opportunities in higher education. The commission on the higher education for women, university of madras in 1979 rightly observed: for women and men college education is necessary for character formation, ability to earn, creative self expression and personal development. The following table will show the picture of women student growth in higher education from 1950-51 to 2005-06

Women Student Growth in Higher Education from 1970-71To 2005-06

Table 3

Year	Men (000S)	Women (000S)	Total Enrolment (000S)	Women as percent of all students
1970-71	1563	391	1954	20.00
1975-76	2131	595	2426	24.50
1980-81	2003	749	2752	27.20
1985-86	2512	1059	3571	29.60
1990-91	2986	1439	4425	32.50
1995-96	4235	2191	6426	34.10
2000-01	4988	3012	8001	37.60
2005-06	6562	4466	11028	40.50

The University Grand Commission (UGC) report reveals that out of 169.75 lakh students enrolled in higher education in 2010-11 almost 70.49lakh were women as compared to just about 47.08 lakh women enrolled in 2006-07

Main Factors Influencing Women in Completing Higher Education

There are different factors which are responsible for influencing women in completing higher education. Some of these are mentioned below:

- In comparison with men, women are more firm in their mission of success. So in education stream also they are strongly motivated to succeed.
- There are many institutions which have the provision of hostel facilities for girl's students. This is also an important factor for girl students to complete their higher studies.
- Women zeal to take equal responsibility of the family pushes them to complete their higher studies.
- Educational institutions meant for girls attracted many conservative families to get admitted their wards in higher educational institutions.
- As they are firm in their mission, so their performance is also remarkable. Thus on the basis of their merit they occupy the domain of higher education.
- There are some courses which provide scholarship facilities for women. This also helps many poor female students to complete their higher studies.
- Now a day the tendency of prejudice against women has been reduced and this helps women to enter in the domain of higher education.
- Increased number of higher educational institutions helped women to complete their higher education.
- Expectation for education –based employment is very high amongst women. This factor works very silently completing their higher studies.
- In some case women students get inspiration from the teachers working in educational institutions which help them to complete their higher studies.
- In most cases women are dependent on male both in economically and in decision making and as such they suffer more. To get relief from this, they go for higher studies.
- It cannot be denied that lucrative scale for the employees working in higher education institutions attracted women in higher studies.

In spite of these it is true that women participation in higher education amongst schedule caste, schedule tribe (both plain and hill) and Muslim community is much lower in comparison with other communities. This is also a serious matter for our country. The government of India should have to take special initiative for the improvement of higher education among these communities.

Proposals for Promoting Women Participation in Higher Education

- Introduce attractive scholarships for both financially poor students and meritorious students to encourage women students in higher education.
- Provide counseling for both family and person concerned at secondary stage of education.
- Improve transport facilities for women students.
- Provide Bank loan facilities for women students.
- Make skill-oriented higher education.
- Education policy has to be taken to facilitate women participation in higher education.
- Establish non-traditional curricular for women and extend state support for this..
- Establish more female educational institutions.
- Increase women teachers in co-educational institutions of higher education.
- Establish post-secondary vocational training institutions for promoting the entry of women in higher education.
- In many cases early marriage leads to withdrawal of women from higher studies. This must be stopped.

Conclusion

It must be admitted that women are in no way lesser than men. They have all the power and capacity as that of men. But they fail to manifest themselves for different reasons. In men dominated society they get rare chance to express their voice. In some cases father or husband create hindrance in their path. They even do not allow them to leave the home for higher studies or work. We should have to change our thinking, our attitude towards women. We should have to think that women are not just reproduction. They have feeling, thinking and all these as the men have. They have all the capacities as that of men and thereby they can do all these as men, if not more. So their power and capacities must be recognized. It is only then women participation in higher education will be enhanced.

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